

DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3237138>

Study of variation in petal number and relative abundance of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* L. flowers

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Received: 13 April 2019; Revised submission: 25 May 2019; Accepted: 31 May 2019

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ABSTRACT: The flowers of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* L. have a wide spectrum of biological activities. The current study encompasses the variation in petal number and relative abundance of night-flowering jasmine flowers. The observed petal number of this flower ranges from four to nine. The most abundant variety is the flowers with six petals, which comprises 60.69% of the total number of flowers counted. The four and nine-petalled flowers are extremely rare making only 0.02% each. This study represents the statistical data obtained directly from the observed natural phenomenon. However, this short communication warrants further investigation to evaluate the correlation of petal numbers of the flowers with other physico-chemical or environmental parameters.

Keywords: Night-flowering jasmine; Flower; Petal number; Relative abundance.

1. INTRODUCTION

Nyctanthes arbor-tristis L., commonly known as night-flowering jasmine or weeping nyctanthes, is a shrub or small tree native to Southern Asia. It belongs to the family Oleaceae. The flowers are fragrant and generally produced in clusters. The flowers, which bloom profusely at night and fall off before sunrise, have white petals with bright orange corolla tube in the centre. A compound named crocetin has been isolated from the orange coloured tubular calyx of the flowers [1]. This tree is well known in India and its neighbouring countries as one of the most versatile medicinal plants having a wide spectrum of biological activities [2]. The flowers possess antibacterial, hepatoprotective, cytotoxic activity, antioxidant activity [3-6]. The leaf extract of this plant has antioxidant activity [7] and the paste of leaves possesses antimalarial activity [8]. Recently, green synthesis of gold nanoparticles, zinc oxide nanoparticles is made using extracts from various parts of this plant [9, 10].

2. CASE PRESENTATION

Simple counting method is used for the experimental purpose based on the number of petals. Fresh flowers are collected from a single plant and meticulously counted. Since, night-flowering jasmine is a seasonal flowering plant; flowers are collected in the month of October at early morning. The plant is located at Mankundu area of Hooghly district.

A total of 4315 flowers were counted in two consecutive years - 2076 in first year and 2239 in second year. The data analysis and graphical representation were conducted by Origin software (Version 8) for Windows. A representative specimen from each of the six petal types have been shown in the Figure 1.

Figure 1. Flowers with different number of petals.

Out of 4315 flowers, 2619 (60.69%) flowers are of six petals, 1238 (28.69%) are of five petals, 430 (9.96%) are of seven petals, 26 (0.60%) are of eight petals and only 1 representative (0.02%) each with four and nine petals (Figure 2). So, six varieties of flowers with petal numbers ranging from four to nine have been identified from a single plant.

Figure 2. Relative abundance of flowers with different petal numbers.

3. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

From the observed data, it is evident that the most abundant variety is the flowers with six petals followed by five, seven and eight-petalled flowers. Four or nine-petalled flowers are extremely rare and hence least abundant. These preliminary but intriguing observations and its statistical analysis may have multifaceted consequences. Petal number varies in response to stochastic, genetic and environmental perturbations. Multi-trait quantitative trait locus (QTL) analysis may be used to identify whether the stochastic variation found in petal number has a genetic basis or not [11]. In Tripura - a state of Northeast India, the flowering phenology of night-flowering jasmine is even used by local people as an indicator of weather forecast such as onset of heavy rainfall etc. [12].

In a study with damask rose, the number of petals and number of stamens have been found to be positively correlated with flower weight [13]. There is also effect of flower size and number on pollinator [14]. Hence, in this case, there might have been some relation between the petal number and pollinator visit to the flower, which warrants further investigation.

Acknowledgements: The author expresses heartfelt gratitude to his parents, Mrs. Bhaswati Pal and Mr. Jaydev Pal for the collection of night-flowering jasmine flowers in an unbiased fashion.

Conflict of interest: The author declares no conflict of interest.

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